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Illuminance Assessment for Construction Facility Safety and Compliance: A Case Study in Construction of a Nuclear Power Plant Site

Amy L. Shepherd, Ryan Bellacov, and David P. Gilkey*

Montana Technical University, Department of Safety, Health and Industrial Hygiene, 1300 West Park St, Butte, MT 59701

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ABSTRACT

Adequate illumination is a fundamental safeguard for construction safety, particularly during night shifts and periods of low natural light. As much as 15% of all injuries are associated with inadequate lighting. This case study measures illuminance from a large-scale nuclear power plant construction project, focusing on the interface between active work zones and high-traffic areas such as pedestrian routes, parking lots, and road crossings. Measured illuminance levels were benchmarked against Occupational Safety and Health Administration safety standards and Illuminating Engineering Society best practices adopted for the project. Findings indicated systemic under-lighting at pedestrian-vehicle interfaces; several locations recorded an average of 16.1 lux, failing to meet the minimum safety requirement of 108 lux. While work zones consistently met safety standards—averaging a robust 2,160 lux—one localized deficiency was detected and addressed through the project's corrective action process. Findings highlight the disproportionate risk associated with underlit transitional areas and demonstrate how applied industrial hygiene assessment can support targeted engineering controls, administrative oversight, and strengthened safety culture on safety-critical construction projects.

1. INTRODUCTION

As of 2026, the United States operates 96 reactors across 54 sites (World Nuclear Association, 2026a). To meet soaring energy demands, federal priorities shifted in 2025 toward the construction of five small modular reactor (SMR) plants and 10 large-scale facilities, aiming for a 400 GWe capacity increase by 2050. Given that nuclear power plant construction projects are massive—often spanning 300 to 1,000 acres—and typically require six to 10 years to complete (Ritchie, 2023), maintaining safety over a multi-year, 24-hour operational cycle is a significant challenge.

In high-consequence construction environments, illumination is a fundamental safety safeguard. Adequate lighting is critical for hazard recognition and the prevention of slips, trips, and falls—which remain leading causes of construction-related injuries (Maynard, Di Pilla, Natalizia and Vidal, 2012). While task-specific lighting is often prioritized in work planning, transitional zones such as parking areas,

* *Corresponding Author:* dgilkey@mtech.edu

pedestrian walkways, and road crossings frequently receive less systematic oversight. This is particularly concerning given that poor lighting contributes to an estimated 15% of workplace accidents (Worksite Lighting and Power Solutions, n.d.).

On nuclear power plant construction sites, the tolerance for preventable incidents is low due to heightened regulatory scrutiny, schedule sensitivity, public visibility, worker and public safety (World Nuclear Association, 2026b). As a result, environmental controls such as illumination must be evaluated not only for minimum compliance (CFR, 2016), but also for their ability to support safe movement and situational awareness under real operating conditions (Singer Safety Company, n.d.). The Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA, 2012) enacted standards for workplace illumination with requirements for activities and environments on construction sites. The illumination standards and best practices guided this project. This case study documents an applied industrial hygiene evaluation of illumination conditions at a nuclear power plant construction site and examined how lighting deficiencies at pedestrian–vehicle interfaces represent a critical, yet addressable, safety risk.

2. CRITERIA AND REFERENCES USED FOR EVALUATION

Illumination measurements were evaluated against project-adopted lighting criteria informed by OSHA construction standards and Illuminating Engineering Society (IES) and American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH) recommended practices. OSHA establishes minimum 54 foot-candle requirements for construction activities, while IES and ACGIH guidance provide higher target ranges of 100 lux intended to support visual performance, hazard recognition, and safety margin (Table 1).

For consistency, measurements recorded in foot-candles were converted to lux using a standard conversion factor (1 foot-candle \approx 10.764 lux). For pedestrian routes, parking areas, and road crossings, the project applied a baseline target of approximately 50–100 lux, reflecting commonly accepted best-practice guidance for outdoor travel paths. Higher targets were applied to active work areas depending on task complexity.

Table 1. Minimum Illumination Requirements (Lux)

Area / Task	OSHA (29 CFR 1926.56)	IESNA / ACGIH Recommended	Minimum Lux Equivalent
General construction areas	5 foot-candles	108 lux	54–110 lux
General indoor workspaces (offices, trailers)	30 foot-candles	300–500 lux	300–500 lux
Warehouses / Laydown / Storage areas	10 foot-candles	150–200 lux	150–200 lux
Mechanical / electrical / detail work	20 foot-candles	500–1000 lux	500–1000 lux
First aid stations	30 foot-candles	300+ lux	300+ lux
Stairways / corridors / pedestrian routes	5 foot-candles	100–150 lux	100–150 lux
Vehicle parking areas	Not specified	50–100 lux	50–100 lux
Road crossings / pedestrian intersections	Not specified	100–150 lux	100–150 lux

- * **IENSA** – Illumination Engineering Society of North America
- * **ACGIH** – American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienist
- * **OSHA** – Occupational Safety and Health Administration

Note: 1 foot-candle (ft) \approx 10.764 lux

OSHA requires minimum foot-candles, while IESNA/ACGIH provide best practice guidance for visual performance and safety.

3. RESULTS

Observed illumination values demonstrated a broad range, from non-detectable or near-zero levels in unlit or obstructed zones to values exceeding 60 foot-candles in areas directly influenced by temporary lighting sources. Lower illumination levels were consistently identified in areas associated with worker access and movement—such as pedestrian routes and parking interfaces—where measurements frequently fell within the 5–20 lux range, while higher levels were observed near fixed or portable lighting installations. These conditions indicate that a subset of the workforce operating in circulation and access areas was subject to repeated exposure to suboptimal lighting conditions during low-light periods.

3.1 Pedestrian and Parking Areas

Illumination measurements across pedestrian routes and parking areas consistently fell below project targets. Numerous locations recorded values in the range of approximately 5–20 lux, with several readings approaching ambient moonlight conditions. The lowest measurements were observed at parking lot corners, pedestrian walkways adjacent to trailers and generators, and designated road crossings. While isolated areas—such as restroom entrances—achieved adequate illumination, variability was pronounced. Bright-to-dark transitions and uneven coverage were common, particularly along travel paths used during early morning entry and evening exit. These findings indicate systemic lighting deficiency in pedestrian and vehicle interface areas rather than isolated equipment failures.

Table 2. Pedestrian & Parking Lighting Measurements

Location / Sub-area	Measured illuminance (lux)	Adequacy noted in report	Observed issue noted in report
Parking Lot SE Corner	10	N	Below OSHA & IES lighting standards
Parking Lot NE Corner	7.1	N	Very low lighting
Parking Lot S Corner (looking N)	5.4	N	Critically low (barely moonlight)
Main road crossing	10	Very Low	Below OSHA minimum; high-risk crossing
SW corner near pedestrian walkway	11.6	Very Low	Still far below target
Pedestrian walkway south end (facing north)	10	Very Low	Unsafe for night use without added lighting
Pedestrian walkway south	5.35	Critically low	—

end (facing north)			
Pedestrian walkway north end (facing south)	20	Low	Improved, but still below best practice
Pedestrian walkway in front of generator	7.6	Low	Increased trip hazard
Pedestrian walkway in front of portable trailer	5.35	Very low	Very low illumination near trailer
Front of restroom	80	Acceptable	Meets general work/amenity area lighting levels
Front of restroom (alternate reading)	5	Very Low	Below OSHA minimum; high-risk crossing
Parking lot north corner (facing south)	~28	Low	Slightly under OSHA minimum
Front of office trailer (south end, facing north)	20	Low	Recommend improvement near entries

3.2 Steel Erection and Work Areas

In contrast, illumination measurements within the steel erection work zone generally met or exceeded task lighting expectations. Crane pads, material storage areas, and office connexes demonstrated adequate lighting during both pre-shift and end-of-shift surveys. One exception was a parking area associated with the steel erection zone, where a negative lux reading was recorded due to uneven terrain and insufficient light coverage. The survey documentation identified this condition as the sole item of concern in the area and recorded both an immediate temporary adjustment and a planned permanent corrective action involving additional fixed lighting.

Table 3. *Steel Erection Area Lighting Measurements*

Location / Sub-area (Steel Erection)	Measured illuminance (lux)	Adequate?	Observed issue	Temporary/Corrective action noted
Crane Pad / Material Storage	30	Y	None	N/A
Office Connexes	20	Y	None	N/A
PE Office Connexes	60	Y	None	N/A
PE Parking Area	-10	N	Uneven ground	Re-position light tower direction (temporary); ordered two 1,500 lumen floodlights (permanent)
Material Storage Area	40	Y	None	N/A
Material Storage Area	45	Y	None	N/A

Lighting ranges were estimated for the steel erection areas pre and post shift following corrective action, see Table 4. Investigators concluded that adequate lighting was present and no further deficiencies were found in these work areas.

Table 4. *Steel Erection Area Ranges*

Survey Period	Reported Range (fc)	Converted Range (lux)*	Reported Conclusion
Pre shift (~0630)	25.56–35.73 fc	275.1–384.6 lux	“Adequate... no items of concern”
End of shift (~1700)	289.5–529.0 fc	3116.2–5694.2 lux	“No items of concern”
* Note. Converted using 1 fc = 10.764 lux			

4. DISCUSSION

The assessment demonstrates a clear contrast between task-focused work areas, which were generally well illuminated, and transitional pedestrian zones, which exhibited persistent and significant lighting deficiencies. This pattern suggests that lighting controls were primarily designed around work execution rather than worker movement and interaction with vehicular traffic.

From an industrial hygiene perspective, pedestrian routes and road crossings represent predictable exposure scenarios with elevated slip, trip, and struck-by potential. Illumination levels near or below 10 lux materially reduce visual acuity, depth perception, and hazard recognition—particularly on uneven ground or in mixed traffic environments. On a nuclear power plant construction project, such preventable conditions carry amplified consequences due to the project’s risk profile and stakeholder expectations.

The documented corrective action within the steel erection area further illustrates the effectiveness of targeted lighting improvements when deficiencies are formally identified and addressed. These findings align with broader research suggesting that simply increasing light levels does not always equate to improved safety or performance. For instance, studies on daytime shifts have shown that increasing illuminance from 500 lux to 2,500 lux has little measurable effect on objective alertness or visual performance because baseline levels are often already sufficient to reach a "ceiling effect". This reinforces the idea that the primary safety risk on a 24-hour construction site is not the intensity of light in active zones, but the variability and uneven coverage in non-task areas. Furthermore, improper regulation of daylight via blinds can also lead to lighting that does not meet standard requirements, necessitating supplemental artificial lighting to maintain safe workplace conditions. Ultimately, the documented corrective actions taken in the steel erection zone illustrate that applied industrial hygiene assessments are effective tools for identifying these gaps and implementing targeted engineering controls.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are derived from the findings of this study and are intended to address the identified gaps in illumination adequacy and associated safety risks. They are structured in line with a hierarchy of controls approach, distinguishing between engineering and administrative interventions, and are further complemented by broader lessons learned from the case analysis. Collectively, these recommendations aim to enhance visibility conditions, reduce pedestrian–vehicle interaction hazards, and strengthen overall safety management practices in operational environments.

5.1 Engineering Controls

- Priority engineering controls should focus on pedestrian and vehicle interface areas, including:
- Installation of fixed or portable lighting at road crossings and parking lot corners
- Supplemental lighting along primary pedestrian walkways and trailer access points
- Repositioning or upgrading light towers to improve coverage and reduce shadowing
- Emphasis on lighting uniformity to minimize abrupt bright–dark transitions

5.2 Administrative Controls

- Administrative measures should reinforce lighting as a routine component of safety management by:
- Incorporating illumination verification into work planning and job hazard analyses
- Conducting periodic lighting audits during seasonal low-light conditions
- Promptly documenting and tracking corrective actions for identified deficiencies

6. LESSONS LEARNED

This case study highlights that lighting adequacy cannot be inferred from work area conditions alone. Pedestrian routes, parking areas, and crossings require equal consideration due to their consistent use and elevated interaction risks. Applying industrial hygiene measurement and evaluation methods to these areas provides actionable insight and supports defensible, proactive safety decisions.

7. CONCLUSION

Illumination surveys at this nuclear power plant construction site identified persistent low-lux conditions in pedestrian and parking areas, contrasted with generally adequate lighting in active work zones. The most significant safety leverage lies in improving illumination at pedestrian–vehicle interfaces and ensuring consistent coverage across travel paths. This case study demonstrates how applied industrial hygiene assessment can identify preventable risks, guide targeted controls, and strengthen safety culture on high-consequence construction projects. We must comment on the proposed resending of OSHA’s illumination standard. OSHA published their intent to resend the standard July 2025 based on the low level of documented violation and citation. We believe that adequate lighting is a critical factor in assuring a safe worksite and operation.

REFERENCES

- Center for Climate and Energy Solutions. (2023). Nuclear energy. Access on April 9, 2026 <https://www.c2es.org/content/nuclear-energy/#:~:text=In%202023%2C%20nuclear%20energy%20provided,in%20realizing%20our%20climate%20goals>.
- Federal Register. (2025). Construction illumination. Access on April 9, 2026 Federal Register :: Construction Illumination
- International Atomic Energy Agency. (n.d.). construction and commissioning of nuclear power plants. Access on April 9, 2026 <https://www.iaea.org/topics/construction-and-commissioning-of-nuclear-power-plants>
- Maynard WS., Di Pilla S, Natalizia D., Vidal K. (2012). Slip, trip, and fall prevention: Concepts and controversies. ASSE Professional Development Conference and Exposition; Jun. pp. ASSE-12.

- Murry, JM. (2025). How to Streamline Nuclear Power Plant Construction. Accessed on April, 9 2026 <https://bipartisanpolicy.org/article/how-to-streamline-nuclear-power-plant-construction/#:~:text=One%20of%20the%20biggest%20challenges,nuclear%2Dgrade%20systems%20where%20possible>.
- Nuclear Energy Institute. (2025). Land needs for wind, solar dwarf nuclear plant's footprint. Access on April 9, 2026 <https://www.nei.org/news/2015/land-needs-for-wind-solar-dwarf-nuclear-plants>
- OSHA. (2012). Safety and health regulations for construction. Subpart D. Illumination. Access April 9, 2026 <https://www.osha.gov/laws-regs/regulations/standardnumber/1926/1926.56>
- Ritchie, H. (2023). How long does it take to build a nuclear reactor? Accessed April 9, 2026 <https://hannahritchie.substack.com/p/nuclear-construction-time>
- Singer Safety Company. (n.d.). Importance of good lighting on workplace safety and productivity. Accessed on April 9, 2026 <https://www.singersafety.com/the-importance-of-good-lighting-on-workplace-safety-and-productivity/#:~:text=In%20industrial%20settings%2C%20the%20role,mishandling%20of%20tools%20and%20machinery>.
- Worksite Lighting and Power Solutions. (n.d.). OSHA guide: Essential temporary construction light requirements you can't ignore. Access on April 9, 2026. OSHA Temporary Construction Lighting Requirements | Compliance Guide
- World Nuclear Association. (2026a). United State of America – World nuclear outlook report. Access April 9, 2026 <https://world-nuclear.org/our-association/publications/world-nuclear-outlook-report/united-states-of-america---world-nuclear-outlook-report>
- World Nuclear Association. (2026b). Safety of nuclear reactors. Access on April 9, 2026 Safety of Nuclear Power Reactors - World Nuclear Association

MAIN AUTHOR

Amy SHEPHERD, CSP, is an experienced Environmental, Safety, and Health (ES&H) professional with more than 18 years of experience supporting complex construction, chemical, oil and gas, industrial, and government projects. She currently serves in a safety leadership role with Bechtel, where she oversees the development and implementation of comprehensive safety programs, regulatory compliance initiatives, and workforce engagement strategies. Amy holds a Bachelor of Science in Occupational Safety from Eastern Kentucky University and is currently pursuing a Master of Science in Industrial Hygiene through Montana Technological University. She is a Certified Safety Professional (CSP) and Graduate Safety Practitioner (GSP) dedicated to advancing worker health, safety, and operational excellence through strong leadership, collaboration, and continuous improvement.

